

Syntheses of Furano Compounds: Part XXXI. Preparation of Some 2-Methyl-3-Aroylcoumarones

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2-Methylcoumarone and its derivatives have been converted into their respective 3-aryl derivatives. The pyrolysis and alkaline degradation of these compounds have been studied.

Elbs reaction has been carried out with success with 2-*o*-toluoyldibenzofuran¹ and 8-*o*-toluoyl- β -brazan². In both these cases the heterocyclic ring does not contain the necessary methyl and aroyl group. The experiments described in this communication were carried out to find if Elbs reaction could be applied in the synthesis of condensed benzofurans starting from ketones of the type (I) and for this purpose 2-methylcoumarone and 2-methyl-4:5-benzocoumarone were benzoylated with benzoyl chloride and stannic chloride³ to give (I) and (III). Both these ketones carbonised on heating without yielding

I, R=Ph
II, R=*p*-Tolyl

III

IV, R=CH₃
V, R=*p*-Tolyl

VI

VII

any of the expected products, e.g., β -brazan and *iso*-dinaphthylene oxide respectively. Similar results were obtained with (II).

The orientation of the aroyl group in (I) and (II) were established by degradation with alcoholic alkali⁴. Thus (I) gave mainly *o*-hydroxy-phenylacetone (IV) and benzoic

1. Buu Hoi and Lavit, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 38
2. Chatterjea and Mehrotra, *This Journal*, 1963, 40, 203.
3. Bisagni, Buu Hoi and Royer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3693.
4. Royer and Bisagni, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1960, 395.

acid and (II) gave a mixture of (IV), *o*-hydroxybenzyl *p*-tolyl ketone (V) and *p*-toluic acid. The cleavage products arise through the intermediate formation of the 1:3-diketone (VI) which undergoes hydrolytic fission as indicated. Both (IV) and (V) cyclise⁵ in the presence of acid to give 2-methyl- and 2-*p*-tolylcoumarone and they were also isolated as their methyl ethers.

It may be mentioned that a useful synthesis of 2-benzylcoumarone was carried out by similar degradation of 2-methyl-3-phenylacetylcoumarone (VII).

2-Methyl-4:5-benzocoumarone was synthesised from 4:5-benzocoumarone by formylation at 2-position followed by Wolff-Kishner reduction.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.s are uncorrected.

2-Methyl-4:5-benzocoumarone. 4:5-benzocoumarone⁶ was formylated by dimethylformamide and phosphorous oxychloride according to the method of Buu Hoi⁷. The yellow solid complex was decomposed with dilute alkali and the mixture warmed on the water bath for 2 hours. Extraction with ether gave 2-formyl-4:5-benzocoumarone which crystallised from alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. 76°; yield 80%. (Found: C, 79.8; H, 4.3. C₁₃H₈O₂ requires C, 79.6; H, 4.1%).

The Wolff-Kishner reduction was done in diethylene glycol in the usual manner at 200° for 3 hours. After dilution with water 2-methyl 4:5-benzocoumarone was isolated with ether and obtained in quantitative yield, m.p. 52° from alcohol. (Found: C, 85.8; H, 5.7. C₁₃H₁₀O requires C, 85.7; H, 5.5%).

3-Acetyl-2-methyl-4:5-benzocoumarone.—A solution of the above coumarone (0.6 g.) in carbon disulphide (6 c.c.) was treated at 0° with acetyl chloride (0.4 g.) followed by stannic chloride (0.8 g.). On working up the ketone was obtained as a crystalline solid (0.4 g.), m.p. 82-84° from alcohol. (Found: C, 80.6; H, 6.2. C₁₅H₁₂O₂ requires C, 80.4; H, 5.9%). The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in red plates, m.p. 242°. (Found: N, 13.8. C₂₁H₁₆O₅N₄ requires N, 13.4%).

3-Benzoyl-2-methyl-4:5-benzocoumarone.—This was prepared as above using benzoyl chloride. The ketone crystallised in needles from alcohol, m.p. 112°. (Found: C, 84.2; H, 5.2. C₂₀H₁₄O₂ requires C, 83.9; H, 4.9%). The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. 264°. (Found N, 12.4. C₂₆H₁₈O₅N₄ requires N, 12.0%).

2-Methyl-3-benzoylcoumarone.—This ketone was obtained by benzoylating 2-methylcoumarone as usual at 0° in presence of stannic chloride. The pink solid complex was worked up after 12 hours to give 2-methyl-3-benzoyl coumarone, b.p. 200°/4 m.m. (Found: C, 81.8; H, 5.4. C₁₆H₁₂O₂ requires C, 81.4; H, 5.1%). The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone

5. Yates, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5376.

6. Stoermer, *Annalen*, 1900, **312**, 308.

7. Bisagni, Buu Hoi and Royer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3688.

separated in red needles, m.p. 276° from acetic acid. (Found: N, 14.1. $C_{22}H_{16}O_5N_4$ requires N, 13.5%).

2-Methyl-3-p-tolylcoumarone.—This ketone was prepared as before and obtained as a liquid, b.p. 160-65°/7 m.m. On keeping, it solidified, m.p. 54-56° from alcohol. (Found: C, 82.0; H, 5.8. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 81.7; H, 5.6%). The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in red needles, m.p. 248°. (Found: N, 12.9. $C_{23}H_{18}O_5N_4$ requires N, 13.0%).

2-Methyl-3-phenylacetyloumarone.—A cooled mixture of 2-methylcoumarone (3.3 g.), phenylacetyl chloride (3.8 g.) in pure carbon disulphide (30 c.c.) was treated as before with stannic chloride (6.5 g.). Gradually a deep brown complex separated. Carbon disulphide was decanted off, the residual complex decomposed as usual and the ketone distilled in vacuum, b.p. 210°/4 m.m.; yield, 3 g. On keeping, the ketone solidified, m.p. 88-90° from alcohol. (Found: C, 81.4; H, 5.9. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 81.7; H, 5.6%). The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in red needles, m.p. 217°. (Found: N, 12.9. $C_{23}H_{18}O_5N_4$ requires N, 13.0%).

Alkaline Degradation of 2-Methyl-3-benzoylcoumarone and 2-Methyl-3-p-tolylcoumarone. A solution of 2-methyl-3-benzoylcoumarone (0.4 g.) in ethanol (5 c.c.) was refluxed for 4 hours with sodium hydroxide (0.25 g. in 1 c.c. water). After removing alcohol the alkaline solution on acidification gave a mixture of 2-methylcoumarone and benzoic acid which were separated and identified.

When 2-methyl-3-p-tolylcoumarone was treated with alkali as above, the alkaline solution on acidification gave a mixture of 2-methylcoumarone, 2-p-tolylcoumarone (m.p. and mixed m.p. 126°) and p-toluic acid. If the alkaline solution is methylated with an excess of dimethyl sulphate, an oily viscous mass separates. This was taken up in ether, solvent removed and then distilled in vacuum. The first fraction (b.p. 60° at 0.5 m.m.) was identified as o-methoxyphenylacetone and the second fraction (b.p. 170° at 0.3 m.m.) contained o-methoxybenzyl-p-tolylketone which afforded a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 210° from acetic acid. (Found: N, 13.3. $C_{22}H_{20}O_5N_4$ requires N, 13.3%).

Degradation of 2-Methyl-3-phenylacetyloumarone.—A solution of the ketone (3.7 g.) in alcohol (10 c.c.) was treated with a solution of sodium hydroxide (1.8 g. in 10 c.c. water) and the mixture refluxed for 8 hours. On working up a mixture of 2-methylcoumarone and 2-benzylcoumarone (b.p. 140-45°/12 m.m.) were obtained (yields, 0.2 g. and 1.8 g. respectively).